

THE EFFECT OF VISCOELASTIC INTERFACE CRACK UPON FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF FOAM CORE COMPOSITE SANDWICH

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SUMMARY

An interface fracture analysis model called three material media model was established for the dynamic fracture analysis of sandwich beam. The three-parameter standard solid material model was employed to describe the viscoelasticity of the adhesive layer. The fracture parameter (J-integral) was obtained based on finite element method.

Key words: viscoelasticity, interface crack, dynamic fracture analysis, sandwich beam

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, composite sandwich structure combined with high bending stiffness to low weight has been widely used in marine, transport, civil construction and aerospace applications. The sandwich interface, which transfers stress and other information between core and facing sheet, is adhesive material with viscoelastic characters. However, due to the anisotropy and nonhomogeneity of composite sandwich, the interface debonding between core and facing is one of the often-encountered failure modes for the structure being in manufacturing or under loads. 错误! 未找到引用源。

Many scholars have been attracted by the research on failure behavior of multi-phase medium interface. Chen and Wang, et al. ^[2] presented an analytical model of a tri-material system consisting of three flat layers with an interface crack. The crack tip fields and fracture parameters of the viscoelastic interface crack are derived by Han, Ellyin and Xia ^[3] through an approximate Laplace inverse transform method. Tang, Guo and Cheng ^[4] studied steady-state crack growth at interfaces for a nonlinear viscous solid bonded to a rigid substrate. Void growth and coalescence in the rate-dependent fracture process zone is modeled by a nonlinear viscous porous strip of cell elements.

With the development of dynamic fracture mechanics, researches on the crack initiation under dynamic load and propagation mechanism have made great progress ^[5]. Cai, Chen and Wang ^[6] studied about Griffith crack in viscolastic layer under mode I load. The dynamic stress intensity factors and energy release rate were obtained based on singular integral equations and Laplace transform. Kirugulige, Kitey and Tippur 错误! 未找到引用源。 demonstrated the feasibility of using functional graded foams as a core material for sandwich structures. Both the experiment and finite element method were used for studying the fracture behavior under impact loading conditions.

A lot of previous research focused on interface crack between two different media, while for the sandwich structure, most of the simplification is not reasonable. The dynamic fracture analysis of the interface crack is rare due to the limitation of either experimental or numerical methods. In this paper, a three-phase medium model is established for the sandwich with viscoelastic interface crack. The fracture parameter (J-integral) is calculated by finite element method. The influence of interface viscoelasticity and loading rate is discussed for a better understanding of the fracture toughness of sandwich with interface crack.

2 THEORY AND FORMULATION

2.1 Tri-Material System Analysis Model and Corresponding Constitutive Formulae

A sandwiched material system, as shown in Fig. 1, composes of 3 kinds of materials, where material F and C denote of a pair of face sheets and core, and material I is the interface. Thus it can be called by tri-material system. Assume a crack that either lies along the interface between materials C and I, or between the materials I and F.

Fig. 1. Schematic model of sandwich material with an interface crack

The constitutive formulae for viscoelastic interface layer is expressed in integral form as

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^t G_I(t-\tau) \frac{d\varepsilon_{ij}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau + \delta_{ij} \int_{-\infty}^t \lambda(t-\tau) \frac{d\varepsilon_{kk}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

where $G_I(t)$ and $\lambda(t)$ are the time-dependent shear relaxation modulus and lamé constant. The formula can be divided into the distortion and dilatation parts as

$$S_{ij}(t) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^t G_I(t-\tau) \frac{de_{ij}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{kk}(t) = 3 \int_{-\infty}^t K_I(t-\tau) \frac{d\varepsilon_{kk}(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

in which, $K_I(t)$ is the time-dependent bulk relaxation modulus.

Assume a three-parameter standard solid model to exhibit the visco-elastic nature of the interface. Hence the shear relaxation modulus and bulk relaxation modulus are written by Prony series form as

$$G_I(t) = G_1 \left\{ 1 - \frac{G_1}{G_1 + G_2} [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_G)] \right\} = G_1 \{ 1 - g_1 [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_G)] \} \quad (4)$$

$$K_I(t) = K_1 \left\{ 1 - \frac{K_1}{K_1 + K_2} [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_k)] \right\} = K_1 \{ 1 - k_1 [1 - \exp(-t/\tau_k)] \} \quad (5)$$

where G_1 and G_2 are the shear modulus, K_1 and K_2 are the bulk modulus, τ_G and τ_k are the relaxation time, g_1 and k_1 are the dimensionless relaxation modulus defined by a Prony series expansion^[8].

2.2 Dynamic J-integral

The J-integral proposed by Rice is one of commonly used crack onset criterions. However, Rice J-integral has not considered the influence of inertial effect by crack body under load with high rate. For this reason, some scholars proposed several dynamic J-integral similar to the J-integral, such as Kishimoto in the literature^[9] proposed a new definition of dynamic J-integral and gave the proof of path-independent. The expression of Rice J-integral and Kishimoto J-integral are respectively given by

$$J_R = \int_{\Gamma + \Gamma_S} (U dy - t_i u_{i,x} ds) \quad (6)$$

$$J_K = J_v + \iint_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{u}_i u_{i,k} d\Omega \quad (7)$$

where, $\Gamma + \Gamma_S$ is an arbitrary closed path enclosing the crack tip, Γ_S is part of closed path on crack face, Ω is area surrounded by Γ and Γ_S , U is strain energy density, $t_i = \sigma_{ij} n_j$ is vector of surface force along the integral path, n_k is outward normal vector of closed path, u_i and \ddot{u}_i are displacement vector and acceleration vector, respectively.

The finite element model for the viscoelastic behavior can be based on a generalized Kelvin Voigt model. Thus, the J_v -integral is introduced by the following partition:

$$J_v = J_v^0 + \sum_{p=1}^M J_v^p \quad (8)$$

$$J_v^p = \int_{\Gamma_1} (F_p \cdot n_1 - \sigma_{ij}^p \cdot n_j \cdot \frac{\partial u_i^p}{\partial x_1}) d\Gamma, \quad p \in \{0; 1; \dots, M\} \quad (9)$$

where M is the number of Kelvin Voigt elements, F is Helmholtz free energy. Further details of the derivation of the method can be found in reference [10].

In this paper, the implicit α -method of Hilber et al^[11] is employed to solve dynamic finite element equations.

3 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Sandwich beam with interface crack

Suppose a fixed supported sandwich beam specimen, a crack between the upper facing sheet and interface is symmetrically distributed at mid-span of the specimen. The lengths of specimen and crack are 200 mm and 50 mm, and the thicknesses of core, facing sheet and interface are 30 mm, 3.6 mm and 0.1 mm, respectively. The lower facing sheet in the mid-span is loaded by concentrate force $2P$. Because of symmetry, only half of the specimen is considered as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Sandwich model with interface crack

The mechanical properties and densities of facing sheets and core are $G_F=10.346\text{GPa}$, $K_F=22.417\text{GPa}$, $\rho_F=2500\text{kg/m}^3$ and $G_C=0.103\text{GPa}$, $K_C=0.224\text{GPa}$, $\rho_C=200\text{kg/m}^3$ [12]. The shear module G_1 and G_2 of the viscoelastic adhesive layer are 1.308GPa and 0.145GPa, respectively, $\rho_I=1200\text{kg/m}^3$, the bulk module $K_I=2.833\text{GPa}$, and assume elastic in bulk [3].

Fig. 3. Time history of J-integral with different initial shear module G_I

For quasi-static numerical studies, the sandwich beam is subjected to Heaviside step-function type loading with magnitude of $P=1\text{N}$. Fig.3 shows the variations of values of J-integral with non-dimensional time t/τ_G for different G_I of the interface. From Fig.3, it can be seen that considering the viscoelastic property of the interface, the values of J-integral gradually increases with the increasing non-dimensional time, but increasing

amplitude gradually reduces, eventually, the value of J-integral tends toward constant. Hence, the hysteresis effect of fracture behavior appears in the adhesive layer.

3.2 The influence of inertial effect on dynamic J-integral

Assuming the relaxation time $\tau_G=1s$, the natural period of the aforementioned fixed supported sandwich beam specimen is about 1ms by calculating. In accordance with the literature [5], the load duration time for a structure is larger than half of natural period of vibration, the effect of stress wave can be ignored in analysis of dynamic fracture.

Fig.4 plots the curves of variation of J-integral value with time for different load rates. The dynamic load imposed on the specimen gradually increases to the same peak value for all the cases, and then remains unchanged. The loading rate is described by changing load time t_p .

Fig. 4. Time history of dynamic J-integral

By comparison of the quasi-static Rice J-integral and dynamic Kishmoto J-integral, the following conclusions can be drawn: (1) the value of dynamic Kishmoto J-integral is depended on load time t_p . With increasing the load action time, the inertia effect decreases and the value of dynamic Kishmoto J-integral approaches to the one of Rice J-integral. (2) The curves of the value of dynamic Kishmoto J-integral with time fluctuate around the curve of quasi-static J-integral with time. The faster loading rate, the more significant the wave characteristic of dynamic J-integral is. Thus, it is necessary to consider the inertia effect in the dynamic fracture analysis.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A three-phase medium model for composite sandwich beam has been established in this paper. The J-integral of composite sandwich beam with viscoelastic interface crack is calculated under quasi-static load and dynamic load. The conclusions are drawn as follow: (1) for the quasi-static loading case, J-integral of sandwich with viscoelastic interface crack is increased with time increasing, but the rate of increase gradually slows down before finally tending to be stable. Thus, it is necessary to consider hysteresis effect caused by the viscoelastic nature of the interface on the fracture behavior of the sandwich material. (2) For the dynamic loading case, with the loading rate increasing,

the influence of the inertial effect on dynamic J-integral is on the rise. Therefore, the inertia effect must be taken into account in the dynamic time history analysis.

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